

TABLE 1—RESULTS OF TITRIMETRIC ESTIMATION OF SILVER; STRENGTH OF SILVER PERCHLORATE SOLUTION: [Ag]=3.054 mg/ml.; FREE MINERAL ACID=0.02080M; STRENGTH OF TITRANT NaOH=0.08927M

Ag taken (mg) ^a	Strength of free acid found (M)	Ag found (mg)	Relative Error (%)
61.08	0.02088	60.94	-0.23
45.81	0.02085	45.68	-0.28
30.54	0.02088	30.54	nil
24.43	0.02089	24.43	nil
15.27	0.02080	15.27	nil
9.16	0.02080	9.24	+0.87
6.11	0.02080	6.19	+1.31

tolerated by masking with potassium fluoride (neutralized using phenol red indicator). Interference by Pb(II) could not be eliminated by precipitation of sulphate as because precipitated PbSO₄ slowly reacts with the reagent solution. Ag(I) has to be estimated after separating it from all these metal ions by usual procedures.

The relative standard deviation in the estimation of silver was ± 0.091 . 60-6 mg of silver were estimated with a relative error of $\approx 1.4\%$.

Discussion

The silver compound, AgSLHCOOH, has been isolated and confirmed by elemental analysis (Found: Ag, 29.38; N, 3.78%; Calc. Ag, 29.35; N, 3.80%). IR study on the ligand, HSLHCOOH and the silver compound, AgSLHCOOH confirmed that the later compound was formed by the deprotonation of the thiol (-SH) group of the ligand. The characteristic bands for -COOH (1735-1740 cm⁻¹) and -SO₂NH- (1335-1340 cm⁻¹ and 1165 cm⁻¹) were found present both in the ligand and in the silver compound while that for the -SH group (2597 cm⁻¹) was present in the ligand but it was absent in the silver compound. Thus the method involves the titration of the acid liberated due to deprotonation of the -SH group of the ligand by Ag⁺ ions. Obviously the protons displaced get bonded to the COO⁻ groups of HSLHCOO⁻ and/or AgSLHCOO⁻. Hence, the equivalence point pH is governed by the ions HSLHCOO⁻ and AgSLHCOO⁻. The pK_{COOH} (3.16) and pK_{SH} (10.32) of the ligand, HSLHCOOH and pK_{COOH} (4.56) and pK_{NH} (10.48) of the silver compound, AgSLHCOOH, in aqueous solution [ionic strength, $\mu=0.5(NaClO_4)$, temperature $30 \pm 0.5^\circ$], reveal that pH of the solution containing the ions HSLHCOO⁻ and AgSLHCOO⁻ will be nearly 6.8~7.6 and consequently phenol red having its colour change interval from pH 6.8 to 8.0^{1b} is a suitable indicator for this purpose.

The free mineral acid in the Ag(I) solution has to be neutralised using the same indicator (phenol red) before the addition of reagent solution, keeping the silver ion concentration 0.01M or lower.

Acknowledgement

Authors express their best regards and record their extreme indebtedness to Professor N. N. Ghosh, Retired Professor of Pure Chemistry, Calcutta University, for his interest and constant encouragement during the course of the work and also for some valuable discussions.

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Studies on the Suppression of Polarographic Maximum of Ni(II) by Na(I), Sr(II), Ba(II), Ca(II) and Al(III) vis-a-vis their Influence on the Kinetics of Electrode Reaction

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Manuscript received 4 December 1978, revised 23 March 1979, accepted 18 October 1979

HEYROVSKY¹, Lal and Srivastava²⁻³ have reported order of effectiveness of some cations in the suppression of the maxima of Ni(II), Co(II), Mn(II) and Pb(II). But all these studies are qualitative in nature in as much as that they describe the influence of increasing concentrations of the cations on the height and position of the maximum. Recently, Singh and co-workers⁴ have attempted the suppression of Ni(II) maximum by some heavy metal cations and also studied the kinetics of the electrode reaction of Ni(II) as a function of concentration of the heavy metal cation from the stage where the maximum just disappears. In present study an attempt has been made to suppress the maximum of Ni(II) by some Uni-, Bi- and Tri-valent cations and then compare the efficacies of different valent cations quantitatively, in term of the kinetic parameter, ' αn_a '.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of BDH AnalaR grade and their solutions were prepared in conductivity water. The depolarizer concentration was kept at $2.0 \times 10^{-3}M$. 0.1 M Sodium Nitrate was used as a supporting electrolyte.

A manual polarograph (Toshniwal CLO2) in conjunction with a polyflex galvanometer (Toshniwal

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PL50) was used for measuring the potential and the current respectively. Experiments were carried out at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Deoxygenation of the solution was done by passing through the solution a steady stream of purified nitrogen gas. The dropping mercury electrode (d.m.e.) consisted of a standard capillary (E. H. Sargent & Co.) which had the following characteristics (in 0.1 M NaNO_3 , open circuit):

$$h_{\text{corr}} = 62.376 \text{ cm, } t = 3.6 \text{ sec, } m = 2.872 \text{ mg/sec, } m^{2/3} t^{1/6} = 2.502 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/6}$$

Results and Discussion

In representative Fig. 1 curve 1 shows the polarogram of Ni(II) in 0.1 M NaNO_3 . Successive polarograms (curves 2-6) were recorded in the presence of increasing concentrations of $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$.

TABLE 1—POLAROGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS

Conc. of Cation M	$-E_{\text{max}}$ V (S.C.E)	$-E_{1/2}$ V (S.C.E)	i_{max} μA	i_d μA	$D \times 10^6$ $\text{cm}^2 \text{sec}^{-1}$	αn_a
NaNO_3						
0	1.24	—	29.516	—	—	—
0.10	1.20	—	24.806	—	—	—
0.20	1.20	—	19.311	—	—	—
0.30	1.16	—	18.055	—	—	—
0.35	No max	1.110	—	16.956	5.75	0.49
0.50	„	1.150	—	14.13	4.93	0.46
$\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$						
$\times 10^4$						
0	1.24	—	29.516	—	—	—
1.0	1.22	—	27.004	—	—	—
2.0	1.20	—	25.965	—	—	—
4.0	1.12	—	21.352	—	—	—
5.0	No max	1.090	—	16.956	5.75	0.57
8.0	„	1.110	—	16.956	5.75	0.53
$\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$						
$\times 10^4$						
0	1.24	—	27.946	—	—	—
1.0	1.24	—	24.806	—	—	—
2.0	1.22	—	20.567	—	—	—
3.0	1.20	—	19.408	—	—	—
4.0	No max	1.090	—	16.642	5.55	0.62
8.0	„	1.125	—	16.642	5.55	0.38

(Table 1 Contd.)

$\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$						
$\times 10^4$						
0	1.24	—	28.888	—	—	—
1.0	1.18	—	24.021	—	—	—
2.0	1.16	—	21.352	—	—	—
3.0	1.14	—	20.410	—	—	—
4.0	No max	1.070	—	16.956	5.75	0.57
10.0	„	1.160	—	16.956	5.75	0.53
$\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$						
$\times 10^4$						
0	1.24	—	29.202	—	—	—
2.0	1.22	—	26.662	—	—	—
3.0	1.20	—	22.137	—	—	—
3.5	1.18	—	20.096	—	—	—
4.0	No max	1.070	—	19.154	6.42	0.67
10.0	„	1.170	—	11.932	3.10	0.32

Common polarographic characteristics worked out from these plots are given in Table 1. The limiting currents in each case are found to be diffusion controlled as evidenced by the linearity of i_d vs $h_{\text{corr}}^{1/2}$

plots. Half-wave potential which is calculated from the intercept of $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log i/i_d - i$ plots, is invariably shifted towards more negative potentials. E_{max} shows a positive shift with an increase in the concentration of NaNO_3 , $\text{Sr}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Ba}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{Ca}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ and $\text{Al}(\text{NO}_3)_3$.

The potential dependent rate constant $k_{r,h}$ for the electrode reaction, $\text{Ni}^{2+} + 2e \rightarrow \text{Ni}$, has been calculated by the method of Koutecky⁴. Having calculated $k_{r,h}$ at various stages of a wave, for different concentrations of the suppressing cations starting from the point of just suppression, the corresponding αn_a values have been calculated from the slope of $E_{d.e.}$ vs $\log k_{r,h}$ plots⁵.

αn_a values :

αn_a values (and subsequent estimation of α) give a measure of the extent to which the kinetics of the electrode reaction is being influenced. αn_a values decrease with increase in the concentration of the suppressing cations. The reduction of Ni(II) is a well established 2-electron process and therefore, n_a , the number of electron involved in the activation step, can either be 1 or 2. Since the decrease in αn_a values is indiscrete and at no stage the two consecutive values vary by a factor of 2, the possibility of decrease in the value of the product, αn_a due to a change in n_a is ruled out. Thus it can be safely concluded that it is the α which is decreasing⁶. α , signifies the fraction of the applied voltage which favours the cathodic reaction⁷, $\text{Ni}^{2+} + 2e \rightarrow \text{Ni}$. A decrease in the value of α thus implies that the transfer of electron/electrons is made increasingly difficult. In other words, the electrode reaction is rendered increasingly irreversible. The shift in $E_{1/2}$ to more negative potentials and increase in slope of log plots are also in agreement with the above conclusion.

Relative Efficacies :

The molarities just sufficient to suppress the maxima are in the order : Al(III) < Sr(II), Ba(II) < Ca(II) < Na(I). Thus relative efficacies of these cations obey the valency rule. This confirms the results of previous workers¹⁻³. At any comparative situation the order of α_n values signifies the extent to which the addition of these cations push the electrode reaction towards the irreversibility from the position in the absence of these cations. In the present study this push towards irreversibility at the point of just suppression is in the order : Al(III) < Sr(II) < Ba(II), Ca(II) < Na(I). Thus Al(III) eliminates the maximum with minimum influence on the kinetics of the electron transfer followed by Sr(II), Ba(II), Ca(II) and Na(I) in order.

Acknowledgement

Thanks are due to Principal, Agra College, Agra for facilities.

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Synthesis of N-Aryloxy (or thio)acetyl/acetamido Pyrazoles and Pyrroles

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Manuscript received 19 May 1979, accepted 25 October 1979

A series of N¹-aryloxy (or thio)acetyl-3, 5-dimethylpyrazoles and N-aryloxy (or thio)acetamido-2, 5-dimethylpyrroles have been prepared to study their hypoglycemic and CNS activities. A slight reduction of blood sugar was observed when six of these compounds were screened on rats at an oral dose of 250 mg/kg body weight. Some of these compounds were found CNS stimulant, relatively non-toxic, induced writhing and piloerections in albino mice.

Several N-substituted 3, 5-dimethylpyrazoles^{1,2,3} and pyrroles⁴ have recently been known to display significant hypoglycemic activity. Some compounds having N-acyl⁵ and N-aryloxyacetyl⁶ moieties have also evinced substantial hypoglycemic efficacy. It seemed, therefore, of interest to synthesise the title compounds, bearing aryloxy (or thio)acetyl moiety. Visualising the CNS activity in some pyrazole⁷ and pyrrole⁸ derivatives, it was considered worthwhile to screen some of these compounds also for their CNS activity.

An aryloxy (or thio)acetyl hydrazine was stirred with acetyl acetone in D.M.F. in the presence of HCl to furnish the desired pyrazoles. The same hydrazine was also refluxed with acetylacetone in the presence of ethanol and glacial acetic acid to give N-substituted pyrroles.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded in sulphuric acid bath in open capillary tubes and are uncorrected. Infra-red spectra were determined on Perkin-Elmer 137 Spectrophotometer in KBr.

Aryloxy (or thio) acetyl hydrazines were prepared by known procedures^{9,10,11}.

N¹-Aryloxy (or thio)acetyl-3, 5-dimethylpyrazoles(I) :

Acetylacetone (.005 mole) and aryloxy (or thio)-acetyl hydrazine (.005 mole) were added to a mixture of D.M.F. (25 ml) and 2N.HCl (25 ml). The reaction mixture was stirred for 10 mts below 20° and then for about 45 mts at the room temperature. The solid separated was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol. Melting points and relevant data of the prepared compounds are given in Table 1.

The structure of the compounds(I) was confirmed by the presence of I.R. spectral bands at 1740-1760 cm⁻¹ (C=O of tert. amide having N in pyrazole ring²), 2900 cm⁻¹ (CH-str.), 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N-) and absence of -NH- str. bands at 3000-3300 cm⁻¹.

N-Aryloxy (or thio)acetamido-2, 5-dimethylpyrroles(II) :

A mixture of acetyl acetone (.003 mole) and aryloxy (or thio)acetylhydrazine (.002 mole) was refluxed in 50 ml of ethanol in the presence of few drops of glacial acetic acid for 6 hr. The crystalline solid obtained on cooling was filtered, dried and recrystallised from ethanol. The compounds thus prepared are recorded in Table 2.